

Point of Impact: Delivering Mission Essential Supplies to the Warfighter through the Joint Precision Airdrop System

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Abstract— Soldiers know firsthand the criticality of having mission essential supplies and equipment arrive at the right place, at the right time. This is of particular importance when operating in remote locations around the world where hostilities are prevalent, terrain is restrictive and mission accomplishment has strategic implications. The Joint Precision Airdrop System (JPADS) is a guided logistical resupply platform that delivers supplies and equipment in a precise manner to Soldiers operating in restrictive or hostile terrain from a high altitude when conventional means of resupply are unavailable, unrealistic or ill-advised. Our current force structure requires a system that can operate in a dynamic and mercurial environment in order to rapidly adjust to changes on the ground. The research paper will explore the JPADS from a Systems Architecture perspective in order to decompose the system and provide critical system details, which will aid in the Design Structure Matrix (DSM) analysis that will follow. The outcome of this research is to not only provide recommendations to the project sponsors working on the JPADS, but to illustrate the value of using Systems Engineering methodologies and tools to analyze complex systems and challenges.

Keywords—*Joint Precision Airdrop System, Systems Engineering, Systems Architecture, Design Structure Matrix, Resupply, Complexity, Decomposition, Stakeholder Analysis, Function, Form*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Joint Precision Airdrop System (JPADS) is a guided logistical resupply platform that delivers supplies and equipment in a precise manner to Soldiers operating in restrictive or hostile terrain from a high altitude when conventional means of resupply are unavailable, unrealistic or ill-advised. Originally, the JPADS concept evolved as a result of a 1996 report from the United States Air Force's (USAF) Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) titled *New World Vistas – Air and Space Power for the 21st Century* [8]. The SAB predicted the USAF would have the capability to deliver cargo from an altitude above 20,000 feet with accuracy between 10-20 meters. This prediction is becoming a reality and the JPADS aims to do just that. Figure 1 illustrates the JPADS Concept of Operation (CONOP) and provides a good frame of reference on what this system intends to do. From the CONOP,

the mission of the JPADS is to execute logistical resupply operations using fixed and rotary wing aircraft in a safe, effective and precise manner in order to deliver supplies and equipment to intended recipients at multiple locations on a single mission in hostile or restricted terrain.

Figure 1: The JPADS Concept of Operations Diagram and Visual of JPADS in Flight [2]

II. STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS

In a military enterprise, particularly during the conduct of combat operations, the characterization of needs is most often conducted according to the intensity of the need; generally weighting the needs of the ground forces highest, as prioritized by the Combatant Commander. A close second is the USAF's needs, again prioritized by the Combatant Commander. Following the needs of the warfighters, the intensity of needs flows down from within the power of the checkbook. Figure 2 on the next page illustrates the flow of materials, technology, information and money for the JPADS system and shows the interconnectedness of multiple stakeholders within the JPADS enterprise.

The primary stakeholder or beneficiary for the JPADS is the ground-based Soldier who depends on the system for

mission-essential equipment and supplies and life-supporting cargo. Other stakeholders in the enterprise are the USAF, Defense Contractors, the U.S. Government, and the U.S. Army's Research, Development, and Engineering Command (RDECOM), which acts as the program's manager and lead integrator.

For the JPADS enterprise, the value proposition or need is to integrate the capabilities of the enterprise's stakeholders to accurately deliver materiel required by the intended recipient at the point of need in a manner that minimizes the hazards associated with delivering and receiving the cargo.

The most practical method of segmentation for this set of stakeholders is to create groups of stakeholders with similar interests. The stakeholders identified may be grouped as follows:

- **Segment 1:** The American government and the American public. These stakeholders, for the purpose of JPADS, are the bill payers. Through taxation, the government collects revenue from the people for the provision of the national defense, from which it allots

funds annually for the military to operate and purchase equipment. In exchange for revenue, the public expects security from the government; and the military, as a tool of the government, provides that security.

- **Segment 2:** The Military. The Combatant Commanders, the ground forces and the Air Force are linked by the common purpose of achieving the government's strategic objectives. Each stakeholder has a very specific role in this endeavor, and they must exchange value in order to achieve their goals (vice acting as independent entities that are not mutually supporting). This segment requires the support of Segment 3, the Material Developers, to provide the equipment necessary for military success and the fulfillment of the government's strategic goals.
- **Segment 3:** Material Developers. The Research, Development, and Engineering Command (RDECOM) works with contractors, such as Argon ST and Atair Aerospace, to develop, test and deliver

Figure 2: Stakeholder Value Exchange Map: Value Flow within the JPADS Enterprise [7]

sustainable equipment to the military in accordance with the military's needs. The RDECOM develops new technologies and works with the contractors to evolve the technology into producible and usable platforms. These efforts are undertaken often with the nation's coalition partners for the purpose of technology/capability exchange and battlefield interoperability. The government regulates this process because it is in this exchange where taxpayer money is spent.

It is important to understand that although the RDECOM is a part of the military, they are placed in this segment according to the role that they play in the process. They are not part of the warfighting effort directly, but instead provide material support to the warfighter.

- **Segment 4:** Battlefield Partners. The Coalition Partners and other users of the military airspace make up the fourth segment of our stakeholders. These groups are also located on the battlefield, but during combat operations they do not provide any benefit to the rest of the enterprise as it applies to JPADS. Airspace users benefit from the reduced number of cargo planes in the airspace and more so from the reduced number of parachutes in the air during combat operations. Because of its precision, JPADS reduces air traffic, which directly benefits everyone in the airspace. It is for this reason that this group is a charitable stakeholder. The coalition partners assist in technology development, and may use JPADS in their own operations, but for the purposes of resupplying American ground forces, they do not play a direct role.
- **Segment 5:** Other potential beneficiaries. Both the indigenous population of the area where combat operations are occurring and the enemy forces may be charitable beneficiaries of the JPADS. Neither group assists in the development or deployment of JPADS, but each may gain some particular benefit. For the indigenous population, JPADS may be used to deliver humanitarian aid to the point of need when access to their location is not possible or practical by ground vehicle. The enemy forces may intercept cargo delivered by the JPADS if the system deviates from its course, but more likely, the benefit gained by enemy forces is a precise location for ground forces executing resupply operations, which will facilitate deliberate operations against friendly forces. Since the JPADS delivers the cargo exactly where it is needed, the enemy can simply watch where the parachute goes and follow it to the ground forces.

The JPADS is a vital system designed to ensure Soldiers operating in an austere and mercurial environment receive mission critical supplies and equipment in a precise and timely manner to complete their mission. Important to fully understand the JPADS is a clear analysis of the stakeholders of the system, which drives decision making within the enterprise. This investigation aimed to provide a thorough stakeholder analysis as a basis for an in-depth systems architecture study.

III. ARCHITECTURAL ANALYSIS

A good architecture is one that meets the needs of the stakeholders in a satisfactory manner and doesn't violate the accepted principles of systems architecture. A suitable architecture is also one that abides by the respective "ilities" that apply to the architectural design, such as maintainability, interoperability, customizability, understandability, to name a few. These apply directly to the architecture's maintenance, evolution, further development, refinement and improvement, as the stakeholders require [7]. The paper will provide a detailed systems architecture analysis of the JPADS beginning with the JPADS top level function, the formal decomposition of the system and the System Problem Statement (SPS). Finally, the paper will cover the JPADS high-level concept tree.

The JPADS exists to deliver cargo to service members deployed in hostile terrain where conventional means of resupply are ineffective. When one breaks down the nature of an engineered system, included in this is the Operand and Processing Element of the system, which makes up the system's function. The Instrument Object makes up the system's form, which is termed the Instrument Object. Function can be defined as "the activities, operations and transformations that cause, create or contribute to performance" or "the actions for which a thing exists or is employed" [4]. The action that takes place is the process and the object that is acted upon is referred to as the operand. The instrument object is the form and also makes up the elements and structure of the system [4]. An illustration of the process nature of an engineered system is shown below in Figure 3. With regards to the JPADS, the cargo is the system operand while the processing function is "delivers." The instrument object is the JPADS itself, which is illustrated in Figure 4. This shows the JPADS top-level function and will be the basis for further analysis of the system from a systems architectural standpoint.

In this section, the paper will move into the JPADS formal decomposition, which will identify the disparate elements of form that make up the system. These include the aircraft by which the JPADS is released during an operation, the USAF Precision Airdrop System (PADS) computer, which is combined with the Army's Precision and Extended Glide Airdrop System (PEGASYS) program to meet joint requirements in order to conduct a precision airdrop and several other elements in the JPADS formal decomposition, which is illustrated on the next page in Figure 6. The dropsonde is a device utilized by the JPADS to collect critical wind data and other atmospheric data prior to the operation. This data assists the Mission Planner (MP) in planning the glide

Figure 3: Process Nature of an Engineered System Illustration [4]

Figure 4. JPADS Top Level Function

path for the JPADS package. The Airborne Guidance Unit (AGU) includes the battery power pack, the Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver, the Guidance, Navigation and Control (GN&C) package and the hardware critical to operate the steering lines in the JPADS to keep the system on course.

The AGU, which uses preplanned data from the MP, data from the PADS component and the GPS retransmission system, acquires its location or position before exiting the aircraft. Once the JPADS acquires its position, the AGU steers the resupply bundle according to system algorithms that determine the trajectory “on the fly” to a specific point on the ground, while simultaneously making corrections in flight through the actuator system on board, which controls the steering lines. The JPADS is a System of Systems (SoS) and this paper will focus on the top-level decomposition of the elements of form shown in Figure 6. In the next section, the paper will move into the JPADS System Problem Statement (SPS) in order to clearly identify the challenge the system aims to overcome.

The primary beneficiary and need for the System Problem Statement diagram illustrated in Figure 5 are the ground forces or Soldiers operating in restricted and hostile terrain. The reason ground forces are the primary beneficiary is due to the prioritization of the need and the fact that the military’s sole purpose to develop a system to meet this need is to fulfill critical requirements of the ground forces. There are several other beneficiaries discussed earlier; however, the ground forces are the primary beneficiaries of the system. Their stated need is to have critical supplies and equipment transported and delivered to them in a safe, accurate and precise manner without damage. The operand and value related solution neutral transformation is annotated in Figure 5 and identifies the intent, function and form.

Figure 5: System Problem Statement: Guided Cargo Parachute System

The original and existing SPS is to design, manufacture and sell a safe, precise and effective air delivery system to resupply security minded ground forces. The function of this statement is to change the location of the lightweight cargo in a timely manner, without damage, by flying in a safe, precise and accurate manner using cargo with a parachute, which will have the means to be a guided system. The revised SPS is to provide our ground forces a product that will transport their supplies and equipment in a timely manner without damage. They will do so by flying their lightweight cargo in a safe, precise and accurate manner. This will occur utilizing a guided cargo parachute system.

For the delivery of cargo to Soldiers in restricted terrain in a safe and timely manner that does not damage the cargo being transported, there are very few processes that may be used. In order to meet all conditions specified by the SPS, the only practical method of transport is flying the cargo to the

Figure 6. JPADS Formal Decomposition

customer. For the purposes of aerial transport there are four processes identified for expansion. These processes are flying the cargo in a fixed wing aircraft, flying the cargo by helicopter, descending the cargo with a parachute and flying the cargo to its intended location in a projectile. The description of these processes are graphically depicted in Figure 7 along with their respective operands, most of which are expanded by specialty.

The limitations placed on the system by both the operating environment and the needs of all stakeholders restricted creative problem solving. This is due primarily to two factors: first, the presence of enemy forces causes an inherent danger to the cargo, the delivery system and the primary beneficiary. Second, the limited budget imposed by the government for the development of a small system such as this one precluded extravagance in top-level system concepts. Creativity, in the sense of this project, is found primarily in the reuse of existing concepts from other military systems [4].

Since the military is a not-for-profit organization with defined budgets and fast acquisition cycles for individual systems, the degree of creativity in problem solving is high

within the given parameters. This is a function of the need to leverage existing systems and technologies where available in unexpected ways to solve new challenges. This type of creativity is precisely what was drawn upon to propose new solutions to this challenge. Each of the top-level concepts in the tree exist in some form elsewhere in the military and could be adapted to deliver the needed value

As this paper demonstrates, a good architecture is one that meets the needs of the stakeholders in a satisfactory manner and one that doesn't violate the accepted principles of systems architecture. An architect must conduct a thorough analysis of all stakeholders within a new or existing architecture in order to clearly identify the direct beneficiary and their goals and needs. This will facilitate detailed planning, development and examination of the architecture behind the system, which will ultimately meet those goals and needs. The paper thus far provides a detailed analysis of the JPADS architecture from the system's formal decomposition to the JPADS System Problem Statement and a detailed analysis on the decomposition of critical functions of the system within the high level concept tree. This analysis will provide great insight into the next

Figure 7: High Level Concept Tree for JPADS [7]

section of the paper, which will utilize the Design Structure Matrix (DSM) to analyze the numerous interfaces and interactions within the JPADS in order to propose improvements to the system.

IV. DESIGN STRUCTURE MATRIX (DSM) ANALYSIS

The DSM is a Systems Engineering and Project Management analysis tool used to model complex systems in order to illustrate where important interactions take place between components and subcomponents of a system, which could lead to opportunities to improve a system, organize a project more effectively or create design teams based on potential iterations, dependencies and rework cycles. “The DSM is a two-dimensional matrix representation of the structural or functional relationships of objects, variables, tasks or teams” [5]. This could have numerous positive implications for improvements to not only the current system, but in the development of future systems. With regards to the JPADS, the DSM will assist in the investigation to identify improvements to the system based on the structural and functional relationships between objects within the JPADS. This section will provide a detailed analysis on the initial DSM of the JPADS and will identify areas where the current system can be improved. Once this analysis is complete, the paper will provide an updated and improved DSM followed by some key takeaways from this analysis.

In Figure 8, the JPADS baseline DSM is shown, which has four main groupings. These four distinct groups are labeled Wind Data Distribution, Cargo Delivery, System Recovery and Conflict. To give an example of an interaction that occurs within this DSM, when looking at the component Dropsonde, the Dropsonde gives updated weather data to the Aircraft, the PADS Computer and the AGU, which is captured by placing a “1” in the box linking the components with the interaction. The horizontal row “gives something” to the vertical row while the vertical row “needs something” from the horizontal row. Another example is the aircraft provides a launch platform for the pallet.

There is one “killer loop” outlined in yellow, which cannot be avoided. The aircraft and the ground forces each give and receive information to and from each other. This creates a killer loop because this information exchange is critical to the operation of the system and it cannot be decoupled.

Once the JPADS goes into operation, the Active Scenario Baseline DSM in Figure 9 captures the interactions that occur, which are primarily between the steering components of the JPADS and the computer software manipulating the controls. The two groups are the Mechanical Steering group and the GPS-Based Directional Control. One might ask what’s missing in this DSM? What key component isn’t captured in the active scenario baseline DSM in Figure 9 that is critical to ensuring operational success?

Over the course of the stakeholder and system architecture analysis, two key aspects of the guided logistical resupply platform were not captured. The two aspects include a terrain avoidance feature and the ability to account for wind and weather fluctuations while in flight. By conducting a thorough systems architecture analysis of the JPADS and then applying

	GPS Signal	Aircraft	Wind Data Sources	Dropsondes	PADS Computer	Pallet	Cargo	Airborne Guidance Unit	Steering Parachute	Blue Forces (Ground)	Red Forces	Terrain
GPS Signal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aircraft	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Wind Data Sources	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dropsondes	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PADS Computer	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pallet	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
Cargo	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Airborne Guidance Unit	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Steering Parachute	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Blue Forces (Ground)	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
Red Forces	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Terrain	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0

Figure 8: JPADS Baseline DSM

the architecture to the DSM, the research provided a visual opportunity to identify “improvement gaps.” Once the investigation provided a detailed DSM with important groupings within the system, it became apparent that both a wind data sensor and a terrain avoidance feature are missing in the design. Illustrated on the next page in Figure 10 is the JPADS System Boundary Diagram, which shows the key components within the JPADS and the numerous interactions that occur between components of the system. Highlighted in blue is the area that is missing the important functions outlined in this paper. With the integration of additional critical goals for variants within the JPADS family, potentially a higher end design for more sensitive military operations, it becomes

	GPS Signal	Aircraft	Terrain	Static Line	Wind	Drag Parachute	Steering Parachute	Pallet	Cargo Net	AGU Chassis	GPS Antenna	Electrical Servoactuator	Battery	AGU Computer	Cargo Padding	Cargo
GPS Signal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aircraft	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Terrain	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Static Line	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wind	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Drag Parachute	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Steering Parachute	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Pallet	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cargo Net	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AGU Chassis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
GPS Antenna	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Electrical Servoactuator	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
Battery	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
AGU Computer	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
Cargo Padding	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cargo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0

Figure 9: Active Scenario Baseline DSM

important to include the additional features.

In order to show what this looks like using the DSM, updated DSM diagrams are included to show the recommended improvements using a wind data sensing device. In Figure 11 to the right, the AGU Wind Data Sensor is added to the DSM to illustrate the interactions that occur between the Wind Data Sensor and other components in the system, to include the AGU and Steering Parachute. The inclusion of the Wind Data Sensor will provide real time wind data to the AGU in order to update the flight path based on changing conditions during flight and on the ground.

The U.S. Army Natick Soldier Research Development and Engineering Center placed a requirement to identify sources with the means to measure wind direction, speed and magnitude at differing altitudes “above a remote stationary position” while interfacing with the Army’s JPADS 2K system. The wind sensing system must have the ability to interface with a computer based ground station and must be capable of “measuring wind direction and magnitude directly above a potential drop zone” for the JPADS. The measurements must occur at 0 feet, 100 feet, 500 feet and 1,000 feet with “additional gates” at 500 foot increments. “The sensing system must have a stand-alone, rechargeable power supply and must be deployable, sustainable and maintainable in all weather and altitude conditions without degradation of measurement precision” [6]. Based on this and previous research and analysis, the project sponsors working on the JPADS confirmed the need to incorporate a wind data sensor into the existing JPADS. The next section will cover the criticality of having a terrain avoidance feature included as well.

The updated DSM that incorporates the Terrain Avoidance System is shown in Figure 11. The groupings remain the same with Wind Data Distribution, Cargo Delivery, System Recovery and Conflict; however, the updated and improved AGU shows new interactions and interactions that no longer exist, which are highlighted in yellow. When the JPADS is in flight, Figure 12 illustrates the new DSM that includes the groupings Flight Path Calculation and GPS-Based Flight Path Following. The improved JPADS with an updated AGU will fly using a three dimensional, GPT-based flight path that can adjust while in flight. The wind data sensor will enable this by drift prediction based on real time wind measurements, which

Figure 10: JPADS System Boundary Diagram [1]

	GPS Signal	Aircraft	Wind Data Sources	Droppondes	PADS Computer	Pallet	Cargo	Improved Airborne Guidance Unit	AGU Wind Data Sensor	Steering Parachute	Blue Forces (Ground)	Red Forces	Terrain
GPS Signal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aircraft	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wind Data Sources	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Droppondes	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PADS Computer	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pallet	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Cargo	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improved Airborne Guidance Unit	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
AGU Wind Data Sensor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
Steering Parachute	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
Blue Forces (Ground)	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Red Forces	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Terrain	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0

Figure 11: Terrain Avoidance System

will require a highly integrated, cooperative design. The new components will include updated PADS computer software, an additional processor in the AGU and a wind data sensor to make this happen. These new components are added into the improved DSM in Figure 12 showing their respective interactions. The inclusion of the Wind Data Sensor and the Terrain Avoidance Feature will lead to a much improved

	GPS Signal	PADS Computer	Aircraft	Terrain	Terrain Model	Static Line	Wind	Drag Parachute	Terrain Avoidance Processor	Steering Parachute	Pallet	Cargo Net	AGU Chassis	GPS Antenna	Electrical Servoactuator	Battery	AGU Computer	Wind Data Sensor	Cargo Paddling	Cargo	
GPS Signal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PADS Computer	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aircraft	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Terrain	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Terrain Model	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Static Line	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wind	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Drag Parachute	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Terrain Avoidance Processor	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
Steering Parachute	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pallet	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cargo Net	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AGU Chassis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
GPS Antenna	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Electrical Servoactuator	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Battery	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
AGU Computer	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
Wind Data Sensor	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cargo Paddling	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cargo	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Figure 12: Terrain Avoidance in Flight

JPADS capable of performing at a much higher level.

As the paper has shown, the DSM is an effective analysis tool that highlights where important interactions take place between components and subcomponents of a system and can assist researchers in identifying critical improvement gaps. This will have numerous positive implications for improvements to the JPADS based on the structural and functional relationships between objects within the JPADS and components critical to design improvements, such as the Wind Data Sensor and Terrain Avoidance Feature.

V. KEY FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In an effort to continue meaningful research in a critical field within our military, there are several future research recommendations that will provide valuable insight to project sponsors continuing work on the JPADS. The first recommendation is to proceed with a detailed architectural analysis on the most improved JPADS variants once details are released on the upgraded systems. This analysis can incorporate the DSM while a second recommendation could utilize an Axiomatic approach in order to fully analyze the improved system. A third research recommendation is to incorporate Robust Design into the JPADS analysis in order to fully evaluate the current engineered Design Parameters (DP) through simulation.

This paper demonstrated that the JPADS is an impressive system capable of meeting a critical need for the Soldiers operating in remote, restricted and hostile terrain. With the introduction of two critical system upgrades, some of which engineers are currently developing, the JPADS will go a long way in ensuring the Soldiers on the ground have what they need to accomplish the mission. With the incorporation of a wind sensor and terrain avoidance feature, our ground forces will have the means to carry out their mission in areas once untouched or unreachable due to logistical challenges. The JPADS will help overcome this challenge, ensuring the U.S. Military has the ability to project logistical support to those operating in arduous and remote terrain.

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